

**IMPROVING THE SYSTEM OF TRAINING FUTURE TEACHERS FOR THE
MORAL EDUCATION OF SWIMMERS**

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Abstract: *All over the world, there are currently contradictions in the development of material and moral qualities. In the process of development of world civilization under the influence of scientific and technological world ownership, human thinking becomes purposeful, rational, purely instrumental and unable to critically analyze the strategic goals of scientific and technological culture. The work of education and upbringing in the country is undoubtedly connected with the development of society, which poses important tasks.*

Keywords: *teachers, ethics, education, folk pedagogy, personal spirituality, teacher training, conversation, social adaptation, analysis, methods and techniques, common technology.*

Introduction The centuries-old experience of the development of our people is analyzed, and the educational process has changed as an important part of social life, based on the principles of the ideas of national independence. The process began with the creation of a legal framework for public education policy. Raising education and upbringing at a high level on the basis of the idea of independence is both an urgent need of our time and a social task of society.

The Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan (August 29, 1997) adopted the Law on Education and the National Training Program. This document marked an important turning point in education. The document clearly defines the basic principles of state policy in the field of education, the education system, its governance structure, the rights and obligations of teachers.

The main goal in the field of education is the determination of democratic, humane principles of education and upbringing, a radical change in the content of the educational process based on the historical traditions and customs of our people, as well as universal human values. open up a wide range of opportunities for initiative.

Methods President Islam Karimov: "In fact, there are no restrictions on educational reform. As long as life goes on, both education and upbringing will be constantly updated and updated in accordance with the new requirements of the time," he said. a new way of reconstruction has created a new model of education.[1;62]

Indeed, the great thinkers of the Uzbek people in their many years of research and discoveries have determined the principles of educating people polite, hardworking and patriotic. The works of our scientists pay great attention to the education of children, hard work, manners and the role of teachers in this work. In particular, according to Nasriddin Tusi (1201-1274), so that a teacher can influence the minds of students, he should feel responsible for gaining the confidence of students and take a place in their hearts. Farobi emphasizes that one of the main tasks of a teacher is to focus on the acquisition of moral standards, as well as practical skills and abilities of youth. According to Ibn Sina, training is a noble and useful activity. He emphasizes that the study of science through the human mind is important in the work of a teacher. In the educational work of Beruni, the goals, objectives and place of education, his views on the development of man and the young generation are built on a truly humane and anthropological basis. The most important of Beruni's pedagogical ideas is the need for a thorough and reliable acquisition of knowledge.[2,72]

The importance of research in the field of public education in the study of the cultural heritage of the past is growing.

Therefore, the generalization and study of historical and pedagogical materials, called folk pedagogy, is of great scientific importance.

The study of Uzbek folk pedagogy, the traditions of mentoring, moral education of young people, including the moral education of young schoolchildren, the use of modern methods of folk pedagogy in the practice of pedagogical activity has a certain scientific value and practical value.

In modern pedagogy, prominent figures pay special attention to the use of the rich pedagogical heritage of the people.

A number of research works have been carried out on this topic, especially in the 20-30s of the last century, which were aimed at training students for teaching activities and the study of teaching activities.

In the conditions of independence of our state, the state education system needs a bright personality of the educator. A modern teacher should be an example of practical high morality, affirm the principles of goodness and justice, strengthen spiritual ties between all people living in our country.

Pedagogical activity remains a practical area of cognition and study of personality, which is a condition for the development of a teacher's personality.

The emphasis is on the psychological factors of moral education, the formation of new thinking. Continuing education creates favorable conditions for the general and professional development of every modern person. Teacher training is an integral part of lifelong learning.

Results The future of our country depends on the general education and training of the young generation and on what moral values they have. In this regard, it is

necessary to focus on creating human resources capable of making revolutionary changes in the economy, enriching culture, and updating the spiritual life of society.

The current stage of development of society presents new requirements for the theory and practice of learning. School teachers are also the subject of research. Scientific research makes a significant contribution to solving this problem. They study the personality of the teacher separately. the importance of a teacher with a wide range of knowledge, pedagogical skills and abilities. Attempts are being made to determine the content of the teacher's professional activity and its organizational components. The importance of ideology, socio-political activity, a wide range of knowledge, the ability to work with children, love for them, a creative approach to work, methodological experience.

Spiritual culture as an important factor in the socialization of a future teacher is the acquisition of values in society and social activity based on achieving social and personal maturity, the ability to independently determine your goals and determine ways to achieve them, is a source of self-confidence.

As you know, the process of thinking is usually focused on finding a solution to the situation, the first stage of which involves a more or less understanding of the problem situation at the model level. How this process unfolds and develops depends on the sequence of creative thinking, depending on the situation. In the process of scientific and creative thinking, depending on the situation, a person makes comparisons, analysis, generalizations.

Creative thinking is an organizational process that determines what a sequence of steps is based on. So, this is clearly an algorithmic process that determines the quality of thinking, that is, the successful solution of practical problems facing a person. The sequence of the search for a solution to the situation is as follows: familiarize yourself with the situation, choose a solution strategy, determine specific actions, compare the results with the situation conditions.

A situation is a set of figurative, verbal and analytical information that reflects the course of events or the result of a specific process of interest to a person. Socio-pedagogical situations are a set of figurative, verbal and analytical information that allows you to draw clear conclusions by observing, identifying and solving the realities of public life. Socio-pedagogical situations play an important role not only in determining the active attitude of students to social and spiritual reality, but also in accelerating their social adaptation.

Discussion It is known that the formation of a person with a high spiritual culture is today one of the priorities of our state policy. The formation of a person with a high spiritual culture is a multi-stage, complex process requiring a technological approach. The technological approach to the formation of spiritual culture requires its feasibility and rational organization.

The basis of the educational process aimed at solving this problem is the expected results and methods for achieving it, planning activities that require modeling of achievement methods, implementing the developed plans and models, and the teacher's educational activities related to managing people's activities and behavior. etc.

The formation of a spiritual culture is complex, and the technologization of this process does not always achieve the expected results: the formation of a spiritual culture is holistic, the pedagogical effect manifests itself in the form of small steps or the gradual formation of individual qualities. The educational effect is gradual rather than parallel; Involving a person in this process is a complex task and requires that the teacher supervise the process from beginning to end. This requires individual skills based on common technology.

Conclusion Based on these results, we can say that the curriculum is designed to improve the system of preparing future teachers for the formation of social skills in students, the project of the formation of social skills in students, and the organization of these processes. The model, as well as the use of the presented methods and recommendations will serve to ensure the effectiveness of pedagogical processes.

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